

GEOGRAPHICAL FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURIST AND RECREATIONAL COMPLEXES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *This article deals with the significant facts about the development of a tourist and recreational complex in Uzbekistan. Moreover, date and the list of place that succeeded the best results in tourism.*

Key Words: *phenomenon, alpine skiing, UNESCO World Heritage List, tourism sector, recreation centers, infrastructure, national parks, nurseries, wildlife reserves.*

Modern tourism is a global phenomenon of the twenty-first century, which is not only a form of recreation and leisure, but also one of the most active forms of communication among people, the development of new territories and a key sector of the economy. Tourism is characterized by the selectivity of spaces, depending on the characteristics and properties of the territory, and on modern motives of tourist and recreational activities. The modern needs of tourists underlie the formation of specialized territorial tourist and recreational systems, which change in space and time. Up to the present time, tourism has become one of the leading sectors of the global economy. In this regard, Uzbekistan pays special attention to the modernization of the tourism industry, the development and improvement of the regulatory framework for the sustainable development of the industry, and the organization of services for foreign guests in accordance with international standards. During the years of independence, Uzbekistan made a significant breakthrough in this area, coupled with the preservation and enhancement of the historical and cultural heritage of the people, the revival of national traditions and customs, the restoration and arrangement of the sights of the republic. The sphere of tourist interests in Uzbekistan includes both active forms of recreation and sports tourism, such as climbing and alpine skiing, as well as traveling for educational purposes, where the object of knowledge is the rich archaeological and religious history of this country.

The presence of Uzbekistan is evidenced by the presence of over seven thousand sites of material cultural heritage of different eras and civilizations, including the historical centers of Bukhara, Khiva, Samarkand and Shahrissabz, included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. In recent years, the country has seen high growth rates in this area (Fig. -1). So, in 2017, 2,690 thousand foreign tourists entered the Republic of Uzbekistan. This figure is 32.7% more compared to 2016, when the number of arrivals was 2,027 thousand people. In turn, during 2018 the number of foreign visitors amounted to 5,346 thousand people and exceeded the indicators of the same period in 2017 by 99%, and in 2019 the country was visited by 6,748 thousand foreign visitors. For 2016-2019 large-scale reforms were carried out in the country (for 2016-2019, over 55 regulatory legal acts were adopted in the country aimed at creating favorable conditions for the development of the tourism sector), aimed at accelerating the development of tourism as a strategic sector of the national economy, which created favorable conditions for significant growth in the sector.

In the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017, there is a tendency that the main number of firms and organizations are registered in the city of Tashkent (321 units) and 70.8 thousand foreign visitors. In Samarkand region there are 57 tourist organizations and 20.8 thousand foreign visitors. In the Bukhara region – 18 tourist organizations and, accordingly, 13.1 thousand foreign visitors. In the Khorezm region – 8 tour firms and 51,2 thousand foreign visitors. In 2017, there are 676 hotels in the country, the number of rooms is 17703 rooms and 34140 places. There are 143 1-star hotels, 2 -star 19 units, 3-star hotels–96 units, 4-star –38 units, 5-star hotels–9 units and 371 hotels without a category . In recent years, new types of travel, including ecological tourism, have been actively introduced in Uzbekistan. The presence in the republic of reserves, national parks, nurseries, wildlife reserves, natural monuments, biosphere reserve makes ecotourism in a very promising direction. In addition, geotourism, medical tourism, sports tourism, as well as mountaineering and rafting have developed in Uzbekistan. Recreation areas and comfortable infrastructure facilities are being built in the regions. For example, in the sports and recreation centers “Chimgan”, “Beldersay” and “Charvak”, located in the Tashkent region, the necessary conditions for skiing and other winter sports have been created. Here are built mountain trails of different types with a length of 300 to 3 thousand meters. Vacationers can climb the cable car using a special lift. The Uzbek mountains are attractive for those who love active forms of recreation such as mountaineering, mountain hiking and

climbing. The most popular highlands of Uzbekistan are the Chimgan Mountains with the dominant Big Chimgan peak, 3309 meters high. This area is the beginning of many climbing paths, hiking routes, climbing, horseback riding routes, ski slopes, etc. A popular rafting route on the rafts is the Chatkal River, which flows into the Charvak reservoir and has rapids of several categories of complexity. For cavers, the Baysuntau ridge with deep caves is of interest: Boy-Bulok (amplitude 1415 m), Festival-Icefall (-580 m), Ural (-565 m); Kiev Cave (-990 m) on the Kirktau Plateau; Zaidman cave (-506 m) on the Chatkal ridge and others. Winter holidays in the mountains of Uzbekistan are organized only in Chimgan and Beldersay. There are several modern guesthouses of hotel type and hotels. In addition, there is a large selection of private sector cottages. Chimgan and Beldersay are located relatively close to the capital of Uzbekistan – Tashkent: at a distance of only about 90 km. Therefore, many lovers of skiing prefer to make day trips to the mountains. The longest ski trail in the mountains of Uzbekistan is Beldersay (3017 m.). Chimgan also has a chairlift, although it is not as extensive as in Beldersay. Its length is 800 m, the upper station is at an altitude of 1925 m. The length of the route is 1500 m. In Uzbekistan, the gastronomic direction of tourism is also gaining popularity, the development of which allowed making pilaf and other national dishes to be a recognized brand of the country. In addition, a sanatorium-resort business is developing in the republic.

Sanatorium-resort business (activity) – a set of all types of scientific and practical activities on the organization and implementation of disease prevention, treatment and rehabilitation of patients based on the use of natural healing resources, studying their properties and mechanism of action, a set of measures for the organization, construction, management of resorts, providing treatment and cultural and community services for citizens at a resort, exploitation and protection of natural therapeutic resources and health protection of resorts. The main type of treatment and prophylactic institution in Uzbekistan is a sanatorium (sanare, lat. -Heal, improve) – a treatment institution intended for the treatment, prevention, and medical rehabilitation using natural therapeutic physical factors in combination with artificial factors, therapeutic physical culture, medical nutrition and other methods in a specially organized mode. There are 71 sanatoriums for adults, 33 children's sanatoriums in the country. Of them, the sanatorium "Mersian", "Chinobod", "ZangiotaZam-Zam", "Botanika", "Buston", "Chatkal", and "HumsonBulak" are the best sanatoriums. Significant role in ensuring the accelerated development of the tourism

sector of Uzbekistan, the formation and maintenance of the country's image on the world market are played by major events regularly held in the country. Nowadays, in the development trend of the tourism and recreational services market in Uzbekistan, there is a significant concentration of territorial units and a differentiation of supply according to the level of development of sanatorium-resorts and recreation organizations. This is especially evident in the example of Tashkent, Fergana, Namangan and Kashkadarya regions, since these regions account for 63.7% of all sanatorium-resort organizations, and the remaining 9 regions account for 36.3% of these institutions.

In conclusion we should highlighted that the intensive development of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan, including respect for the historical and cultural heritage, the creation of infrastructure that fully meets international standards, the strengthening of international relations have turned our region into one of the most visited countries in the world.

REFERENCES:

1. Александрова А.Ю. Международный туризм Учебник.– М., 2002.
2. Туризм в Республике Узбекистан. Анализ статических данных. Госкомстат Узбекистана.–Ташкент,2018
3. <https://cyberleninka.ru/search?q=Karakulov%20Nurbol%20Maidanovich&page=1>
4. The Role of the Tourist and Recreation Complex in the Strategy of Development of the Tourist Industry of Uzbekistan Usmanova Zumrad Islamovna 2021.